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Pseudonym as an Anthroponymic Category

Avezova Dilovar Salimovna

Teacher of the Russian language department and literature Faculty of Philology Bukhara State University

Annotation: *The article talks about pseudonyms of the twentieth century, in particular about the place of pseudonyms in the anthroponymic system of the national language, the history of the study of pseudonyms, functional load, choice of nominative forms, motives and principles of pseudonymous names, the degree of informativeness.*

Key words: *pseudonym, functional load, nominative form, motives, principles, nomination, informativeness.*

Statement of the problem in a general way ... pseudonyms occupy an important place in the anthroponymic system of the national language, they are a kind of proper names of people and are designed to hide their real name or surname. The scientists focused on the problem of the linguistic status of the pseudonym, as well as the purpose, function and nomination, in the structure of the class of pseudonyms, etc. The problem of constructing a complete thematic classification of the pseudonymicon, taking into account the dynamics of modern socio-cultural communication in its comparison with the development of self-designation in previous periods of the history of the national language, is also insoluble. When identifying the integral features of a pseudonym, it is necessary to take into account the linguistic status of this nomination, the scope, and the duration of use, because different classes of pseudonyms have their own characteristics. We highlight the following defining features of the pseudonym: signs of lexical semantics:

- a) the secondary name of the person;
- b) an optional name, unregulated by legislation;
- c) the name is mainly indicated by its informativeness and characterization;
- d) a name that, depending on the sphere of use, may acquire certain connotations and perform additional functions in this regard (evaluative, symbolic, aesthetic, etc.); sociocommunicative and functional signs:

- a) the informal name of a person, but can be used in official situations;
- b) the pseudonym has a special purpose-to protect the secret of the real naming of the carrier;
- c) a pseudonym performs a special function-an esoteric one, which is not inherent in other anthroponyms;
- d) the use of a pseudonym is associated with the social activities of the bearer (writers, journalists, actors, etc.; socio-political figures, criminal elements);
- e) pseudonyms can be self-names (literary and artistic) or provided by the environment (most socio-political, criminal);
- f) the functional load of a pseudonym depends on its variety: for example, literary and artistic self-names can acquire permanence and take over a person's real name, becoming an iconic element of cultural history, a precedent phenomenon, while others are characterized by use only for a certain period – as long as they use the bearer himself; there is) a pseudonym that it becomes the only name of a person, loses its specificity and passes into another anthroponymic category;

g) pseudonyms are not inherited; c) a person may have one, several or many aliases [4, pp. 7-8]. The formulation of the objectives of the article... The purpose of this article is to reveal the features of the pseudonym regarding the functional load, the choice of nominative forms, place in the National Anthroponymicon, and the like. Presentation of the main material ... it was noticed that the ratio of functions in aliases of different classes is not the same. In political pseudonyms, after the nominative, the esoteric function comes to the fore, and then additional functions can be superimposed: characteristic, evaluative, expressive, symbolic, etc. In the pseudonyms of cultural figures-writers, journalists, actors, singers, etc., we observe polyfunctionality, that is, another/ others are necessarily superimposed on the main function, therefore the creative person often uses self-designation to manifest his ideological credo [4, p. 10]. *Philological Discourse*, Issue 9, 2019 / *Philological Discourse*, Issue 9, 2019 217 The question of choosing nominative forms is also important when considering the nominative features of a pseudonym. This choice is due to both the general patterns of occurrence of lexical units and the specifics of the means of secondary naming. Ready-made words are used as an alias or new ones are created. In addition to pseudonymous words, asterisks (asterisks), initials, and ciphers act as a means of secondary nomination. The common name of encrypted signatures is cryptonyms [4, p. 10]. In the National Anthroponymicon, pseudonyms occupy an intermediate place between the core (first names, surnames, patronymic names) and peripheral (nicknames) names of people. Aliases have both common and differential features with these units of proprietary vocabulary. One of the distinguishing features between surnames, personal names and patronymic names and pseudonymous forms is their word-forming patterns. A special similarity can be traced between a pseudonym and a nickname: pseudonyms and nicknames are means of secondary nomination of a Person; their use is optional, optional; most pseudonyms, like nicknames, are endowed with informative and characteristic potential; they are not legally interpreted. However, pseudonyms and nicknames are different anthroponymic categories. The main difference lies in the purpose and scope of use of these informal names of people. Firstly, a pseudonym, unlike a nickname, has a special purpose-to hide the real name of the bearer; secondly, pseudonyms are used by representatives of certain social groups and related to their social activities. They are mainly used by cultural figures and public and political figures. In addition, pseudonyms, as a rule, are the result of the self-naming of the bearer of an assumed name (with the exception of political and criminal ones). The bearers receive nicknames from the environment [4, p. 11]. Note that the subject of discussion is still the content of the term "nickname", which is used in several meanings: the same as a zoonym; a conspiratorial nickname of a person; a comic nickname [5, p. 65]. In underground and criminal circles, Klitschko is a "conspiratorial name or surname" that performs the esoteric function of a pseudonym. That nickname,

in our understanding, is a kind of pseudonym, an outdated name for its designation. The inextricable interrelation of personal self-determination and comprehension of the surrounding world is also confirmed by the dialogical concept of the nature of personality consciousness by M.M.Bakhtin. Its main idea is that the formation of a personality and its identity is possible only through interaction, that is, dialogue with others, which is a component of personal and social existence, the so-called event of individuals. M.M.Bakhtin rethinks the classical objectivist version of the understanding of identity and self-identification of a person, focused on considering it as transcendent in relation to other monologized subjects. Thinking, consciousness and the process of self-identification of a person cannot occur in isolation, individually, but is formed in a dialogical space, developing on the basis of a dialogue with other thoughts and ideas: "The true life of a personality is accessible only to dialogical penetration into it, to which it responds and freely reveals itself."² The dialogical concept of M.M.Bakhtin has similarities with the views of O.Rosenstock-Hussey, according to which it is in dialogue with other people that the human Self is born, which arises as a response to the call of the surrounding world. Rosenstock-Hussey considers dialogue as the foundation of a genuine human existence, focused "on revealing the invisible" - what was before a person was born and will exist after his death, that is, establishing a connection between generations within everything. Thus, another group of reasons for creating pseudonyms is involuntarily highlighted, where a pseudonym is one of the ways of self-expression of the author, the result of self-identification and expression of the author's attitude to his own work, awareness of himself in the creative space. Summarizing the above, it is worth noting that the self-identification of a creative personality occurs under the direct influence of the cultural and social environment around, in other words, the principles of the concept of dialogue are fulfilled: the personality transforms itself under the influence of dialogical communication with the outside world, and the dialogue has a multi-directional character. Creativity and other ways of self-expression and self-identification of a creative personality are particularly noticeable results of such influence. These may include creating and choosing an alias.

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